

Deliverable 2.3

Year 3 intervention designs: a summary report and compilation of design challenges, design briefs and wireframes

Work Package: WP:2 Year 3 intervention designs: a summary report and compilation of design challenges, design briefs and wireframes

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Abstract (for public dissemination only)	<p>The GREAT project conducts case studies which explore how games-based activities can provide insight into citizens views which is of value to policy stakeholders. This report describes the design of case study interventions carried out in collaboration with policy stakeholders and game studios in year three of the project. Five case studies are summarised, each with a policy sponsor. The outcomes are two designs for implementation in a dilemma-based serious game, and three designs for surveys delivered through a web app to players of commercial games. It is concluded that the work of WP2 in 2025 and across the project shows that such collaborations are possible, but that stakeholders prefer a consultancy model with feedback rather than a time-intensive collaborative process. Successful collaboration with game studios requires expert skills and can be conditioned by economic and political factors. The implications for GREAT project objectives and research questions are discussed.</p>
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List of Abbreviations

CO	Confidential
CEO	Chief Executive Officer
DG ENER	Directorate-General for Energy
DiBL	Dilemma Based Learning
DMP	Data Management Plan
DoA	Description of Action
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EC	European Commission
ESD	Education for Sustainable Development
EESD	Unit of Education for Environment and Sustainable Development, Ministry of Education, Cyprus
GA	Grant Agreement
GCS	GREAT Case Study
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulations
H2020	Horizon 2020 program of the European Union
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
OER	Open Educational Resources
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal
UNICEF	United Nations Children's Fund
UNDP	United Nations Development Programme
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the results of GREAT WP2 work in 2025 and adds reflections which cover both this work and the results of WP2 across the project as a whole.

GREAT WP 2 Intervention Design has two main responsibilities in the project. Firstly, it ensures that the case studies carried out by the project address the real needs of policy makers and other policy stakeholders. Secondly, it collaborates with policy stakeholders and games providers to generate detailed effective designs for interventions and instruments. The completed designs are then implemented in WP3 by the game platforms participating in the project: the serious games platform DiBL from partner SGI, and the PlanetPlay survey app which can be embedded in commercial games to gather the views of large numbers of players. The present deliverable summarises the work carried out by WP2 during year three of the GREAT project.

In 2025, the final year of the project, seven case studies were active. In two of these it became clear at an early stage that it would not be possible to proceed to the design of an intervention, and they were terminated. In the remaining five case studies in these there was a total of 41 participations of policymakers in design activities ranging from discussion of themes and dilemmas to detailed design work. 70 games studios were engaged in some way in these activities, ranging from initial discussions of opportunities to detailed decision making on designs. These have led to wireframes and other documents specifying two DiBL games, and three PlanetPlay interventions. In the main body there is a summary of each design step for each case study, with more details available in the confidential annexes, with Annex 1 containing all the planning and reporting documents, and Annex 2 consisting of a zip file containing supplementary material referenced in the main body. This large body of evidence gathered by WP2 in 2025, and across the project, together with the interviews carried out, provides a rich resource for further analysis and research findings.

A key feature of GREAT is that the consortium does not include any policymakers, and only one games company (SGI focusing on serious games) and one company focusing on the information flows between games studios and policymakers (PlanetPlay). This ensures that WP2 activities carried out with policymakers and games studios are authentic, in that they respond to real-world needs, rather than the simply fulfilling the targets of a funded project. In engaging policy stakeholders and game studios in designing interventions insight has been gained both into how to do this most

effectively (WP2 objective 1) and into the benefits concerns and risks of stakeholders which enable and constrain these collaborations (WP2 objective 2). As described in the conclusions section, both WP2 and the project as a whole have tested the proposition that the services offered by the project would be so compelling that stakeholders would be motivated to contribute their effort to collaborations in the design and execution of case studies. The work of WP2 in year 3, and throughout the project, has shown that policy stakeholders and games companies can indeed be engaged, and a successful programme of designing interventions has been carried out. However, the intensity of collaboration with stakeholders has been lower than had been hoped for.

Interviews conducted by WP2 with 8 stakeholders, and the transcript of a GREAT round table involving nine leading games companies, showed that this was not due to a perceived lack of benefits from the services offered by GREAT. Policy stakeholders are aware of their need for information and are pleased with the benefits of the information which GREAT can generate, while games companies are enthusiastic about the benefits of leveraging their games and links with players to achieve socially beneficial outcomes. Rather, time pressure from competing priorities has been the main constraint on both policy stakeholders and games companies. In the case of games companies this has been particularly intense because of the current pressure on games companies, and accompanying redundancies, which has focused their attention on core business processes. At the same time both policy stakeholders and games companies have been reluctant to widen the scope of collaborations to include other organisations or citizens, because of the risk which they perceive of losing control of work done in their name. This has been compounded by the inequality inherent in a funded project requesting input from organisations and citizens who are not recompensed for the time which they invest. The result of these constraints has been an inexorable movement towards a more consultancy-based model of collaboration as the only effective option, rather than true co-design. The policy stakeholders themselves have expressed their satisfaction with this model and feel that they have collaborated fully in project activities.

1. Introduction

D2.3 is the third and final deliverable reporting on the work of GREAT WP2. As such, it presents the results of the year 3 activities relating to the design of the interventions carried out in the case studies organised by WP4. The intervention designs are the result of collaborations with stakeholders, including both policy stakeholders and games companies. It also reports on consultations with stakeholders which provide insight into the opportunities and constraints which have moulded the work, and which inform future work.

The objectives of WP2, and their relationship with the wider goals of the GREAT project are discussed in detail in D2.1. The objectives are:

WP2 Objective 1: To ground project activities in authentic policy dilemmas, in actual challenges of social participation, and in the needs of policymakers.

WP2 Objective 2: To produce specifications and design documents which enable WPs 3, 4 & 5 to configure, build, deploy, and analyse games that generate data that can inform policy outputs.

The work of WP2 corresponds to the first three steps in the case study cycle which has been established by the project (see figure 1). The activities of WP2 provide support for WP4, which selects the case studies, manages and documents them. Accordingly, the organisations with which WP2 collaborates, and the context within which that collaboration takes place, are determined by WP4.

D2.3 follows the structure of D2.1 and D2.2, grouping together the work done in each of the three design steps across case studies active in 2025. This preserves the comparability of the work done across the three years of the project. However, the reflections on each step are rather shorter in D2.3, as this discussion is partly merged with the *Conclusions* section.

In the *Conclusions*, we reflect on the work of this reporting period and link it to an analysis of that carried out in the project as a whole.

Figure 1: Steps 1 to 3 (WP2) of the GREAT methodology

2. Policy stakeholders and game studio participation

Activities relating to six case studies are reported here, involving six different policy stakeholders (see table 1 below). The GREAT project examines the ways in which games can facilitate citizens' expression of their views in ways which can benefit policy stakeholders. In doing so it has prioritised authenticity, identifying stakeholders from outside the project who do not receive project funding, and giving them an important role in activities which are critical for achieving project objectives. The reward for this strategy is that the work of the project continually engages with the real-world opportunities and constraints which determine the success or failure of the GREAT approach. The concomitant risk is that project activities may be compromised by the decision of a stakeholder to withdraw or constrain their collaboration, for reasons which

may be entirely reasonable. This dynamic is prominent in the work of WP2, and we offer reflections on what has been learnt in this respect.

Table 1: Brief descriptions of policy stakeholders engaged.

Stakeholder	Area	Description
Waterwise	UK	Waterwise is an independent group seeking to minimise wastage and where possible devise ways of making water go further (recycling, reusing). The group is composed of experts in water efficiency policy, regulation, research, behaviour, and campaigns. Waterwise effects change by being open to new ideas and testing them, bringing partners together to demonstrate efficient water use approaches and collaborations, drive policy agendas to change the law, collect and disseminate evidence, and campaign on water efficiency. https://waterwise.org.uk/
New Automotive	UK	New Automotive seek to increasing the pace of the clean energy transition with a focus on road transport. They use data to develop persuasive stories, informing the public and influencing future policy development. They also inform the public to create deeper understanding of the current revolution in personal transport. To this end, they develop briefings, policy papers, and reports using data to provide insight and analysis on the current state of the switch to electric vehicles. https://newautomotive.org/
Department of Fisheries Forestry and the Environment	South Africa	The DFFE Provides leadership in environmental management, conservation and protection towards a sustainable development and a climate resilient South Africa, for the benefit of all South Africans and the global community. https://www.dffe.gov.za/
UNDP	Global	The United Nations Development Program has the mandate to end poverty, and to build democratic governance, rule of law, and inclusive institutions. The UNDP helps countries develop policies, leadership skills, partnerships, and institutional capabilities to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals. https://www.undp.org/
Ministry of Education of Cyprus	Cyprus	The Ministry of Education is responsible for running primary, secondary, technical and vocational, and higher education. Within the Ministry, the Unit of Education for Environment and Sustainable Development, under the Cyprus Pedagogical Institute, supports national ESD implementation through teacher training, resource

DG ENER	Europe	<p>development, and school-wide capacity building. https://www.moec.gov.cy/en/</p> <p>The Directorate-General for Energy develops and supports the implementation of the Commission's policies on energy. The EU's energy policy priorities include investing in clean energy, making energy affordable for households and companies, and ensuring access to secure and diversified energy supplies, including by eliminating Europe's dependency on Russian fossil fuels. https://commission.europa.eu/about/departments-and-executive-agencies/energy_en</p>
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These stakeholders were involved in six case studies during 2025, with 15 case study cycle steps being carried out, as summarised in Table 1, and in the summaries below. Collaborations with New Automotive and DG ENER were terminated before reaching the end of the design process. Detailed information about the work carried out is available in the planning and reporting documentation in *D2.3 Annex 1 Planning and Reporting*. Additional documentation, such as presentations, meeting notes and Miro board downloads, is provided in D2.3 Annex 2 Supplementary Material. Both these annexes are confidential, to protect the privacy of the discussions with stakeholders.

Table 2, below, provides an overview of the key features of the activities carried out. It can be seen that there was a total of 41 participations from policy stakeholders in design activities. Throughout the project, a list of studios who were interested in participating was maintained, and this reached 70 by the date of reporting. These were contacted and briefed each time an opportunity for collaboration arose. The tools used were largely the standard collaboration tools found in organisations: email, voice/video calls, collaborative documents (Google Docs in these activities), and office applications, primarily PowerPoint and Excel. The only specialised tool used was Miro, for design of wireframes, and this was only used in a particularly complex design. The activities were mostly remote, reflecting the geographical distribution of participants, with some face-to-face activities where feasible.

It will be noted that two of the case studies did not complete the intervention design process and were discontinued. Both of these were to have used the PlanetPlay approach, and this has reduced the number of collaborations with games studios. In two case studies, GCS2(b) Waterwise and GCS9 Play2Act3, the final aspects of the design are being finalised at the time of writing

Table 2: design activities conducted with stakeholders, ordered by step and case study

Step	Case study	Lead	Policy Stakeholder	Context	Policy participants	Game Studio Participants	Tools	Mode
1	GCS 2(b)	UB	Waterwise	UK	1 F		Email, voice/video calls.	Remote
1	GCS 6	UB	NewAutomotive	UK	1 M		Email, voice/video calls.	Remote
1	GCS 7	UNIR	DFFE SA	South Africa	6 F, 3 M		Email, face-to-face meetings.	Mixed
1	GCS 8	UB	UNDP	Global	2 F		Email, voice/video calls.	Remote
1	GCS 9	UB	UNDP	Global	3 F		Email, voice/video calls.	Remote
1	GCS 10	FU	Ministry of Education of Cyprus	Cyprus	2 F		Email, voice/video calls.	Mixed
2	GCS 2 (b)	UB	Waterwise	UK	1 F		Email, voice/video calls, gDocs.	Remote
2	GCS 6	UB	NewAutomotive	UK	1 M		Email, voice/video calls.	Remote
2	GCS 7	UNIR	DFFE SA	South Africa	0		Email, voice/video calls, gDocs, Excel.	Remote
2	GCS 8	UB	UNDP	Global	2 F		Email, voice/video calls, gDocs.	Remote
2	GCS 9	UB	UNDP	Global	2 F		Email, voice/video calls, gDocs.	Remote
2	GCS 10	FU	Ministry of Education of Cyprus EESD/ Cyprus Energy Agency	Cyprus	6 F 1 F		Email, voice/video calls Miro, ppt., gDocs.	Remote
3	GCS 2(b)	UB	Waterwise	UK	1 F, 1 M	70 contacted	Email, voice/video calls, gDocs, ppt	Remote
3	GCS 7	UNIR	DFFE SA	South Africa	0		Email, voice/video calls, gDocs, Excel, Miro.	Remote
3	GCS 8	UB	UNDP	Global	2 F	70 contacted, 4 participated	Email, voice/video calls, gDocs, ppt.	Remote
3	GCS 9	UB	UNDP	Global	2F	70 contacted	Email, voice/video calls, gDocs, ppt.	Remote
3	GCS 10	FU	Cyprus Ministry of Ed. EESD Cyprus Energy Agency	Cyprus	2 F, 1M 1 F Totals: 34 F 7 M		Email, voice/video calls, gDocs, ppt.	Mixed

To maintain consistency and comparability, this deliverable maintains the structure adopted in D2.1 and D2.2. Accordingly, the descriptions of activities are organised by the three steps of the GREAT cycles, rather than by case study, in order to draw out the lessons learned for each step in the methodology. Longitudinal accounts of case studies are provided in the deliverables of WP4.

2.1 Additional data gathering

To inform reflection on the work carried out in WP2, the team conducted a series of semi structured interviews with stakeholders who were involved in the project. Two interviews were conducted with games studios, and four with policy stakeholders. Two related but distinct question sets were developed for the interviews and shared with the respondents before the interviews took place. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, using a standard form. The documentation of questions and informed consent form is provided in the appendix to this deliverable.

The interviews were carried out by Dai Griffiths and Natalia Padilla-Zea (both of UNIR) and involved the following interviewees:

Table 3: Interviews conducted in WP2

Name	M/F	Role and organisation	Policy / Game
Amit Khanduja	M	CEO Reliance Entertainment	Games
Emily Thornton ¹	F	Water Efficiency Programme Co-Ordinator, Waterwise	Policy
Marina Kyriakou	F	Board director of Urban Gorillas	Policy
Silvia Tovar Jardon	F	UNDP. knowledge coordination specialist in UNDP climate hub	Policy
Mathias Norwig	M	CEO Sybo	Games
Marios Antoniou	M	Cyprus Ministry of Education, Unit for Education for the Environment and Sustainable Development	Policy
Patty Alleman & Raquel Abifadel	F F	UNICEF	Policy

¹ This interview is not discussed in D2.3, as approval for use of quotations has not been received.

Additionally, an interview was carried out with members of PlanetPlay, the GREAT partner which is responsible for collaborations with game studios.

Jude Ower	F	Chief Strategy Officer, and Technical	Games
Joost Schuur	M	Product Manager, PlanetPlay	

Further data was obtained in the transcript of a round table conducted in the Danish Embassy in New York on 24 September 2025, under the aegis of The New York Climate Week. The participants included Xbox, CleanPlay, The Raine Group, Creative Denmark, Tencent, Unity Technologies, UNICEF, Standard Game Studios, Games for Change, Sybo, Roblox, and Reliance Games, as well as academics and creatives.

Additional relevant material is also available in an interview conducted in the context of WP5, and available in the mid-term evaluation deliverable D5.2, page 31-33 (societal impact, policystakeholder /Green Jobs)

Chiara Cardelli	F	Program Manager, Klima und Energiefonds	Policy
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3. Step one: What the study will achieve

In the Case Study Protocol (see D4.2), step 1 of the case study cycle is an activity which determines what the case study will achieve and with whom. In such an activity, GREAT collaborates with a problem owner, i.e. a stakeholder organisation (or group of stakeholders) that has agreed to partner with the project to carry out a case study. The outcomes of this work are intended to identify:

- The most relevant current dilemmas faced by the problem owner.
- The insight and evidence the problem owner would like to obtain about citizens' attitudes and preferences.
- Indicators, i.e. decisions, choices or behaviours that would indicate citizens attitudes and preferences.
- The groups of citizens and organisations who should be involved if the problem owner is to obtain accurate and representative information.

The activities carried out to address this step in the second year of the project are summarised below. Note that most of the work on GCS4 was reported in D2.1, and only step 3b is included here.

3.1 GCS2(b) Waterwise step 1

Context

Waterwise) is a water-and-sustainability-related group of United Kingdom stakeholders who campaign for a wise use of water. The work reported here is described as (b) because it is part of an on-going case study with Waterwise, reported in D2.2, designing a new intervention to address a similar dilemma. There is an opportunity to gather more focused, quantitative information using the PlanetPlay infrastructure. In addition to generating additional useful information for the policy stakeholder, the work enabled GREAT to examine how longer serious games could feed into a survey-based inquiry delivered in a commercial game. As a result, the design steps were undertaken for a second time, with the same case study sponsor, Waterwise.

Activities

The activities built on the outcomes of the Waterwise DiBL game to identify a focus for a PlanetPlay survey. The Waterwise DiBL results were shared by email with the Head of Finance and Commercial Services at Waterwise. The first step was taken by the project team, proposing to build on the Waterwise DiBL results through a survey. This was well received by Waterwise, and the GREAT team were advised to hold discussions with The Head of Policy and Research. This led to a meeting which discussed the outcomes of the DiBL, to identify a topic for a further stage of data gathering.

Results

Discussions with the Waterwise Head of Policy and Research highlighted three topics for the PlanetPlay survey:

- Public opinions on hosepipe bans
- Sustainable water use education
- Informing building regulations on public support for water re-use/harvesting

Follow up email conversations indicated that topic 3 would best build on the insights gathered in the Waterwise DiBL. Interest was expressed in investigating if the survey could be gamified to investigate if this format resonates within gaming communities. This possibility was explored in Step 2.

Lessons learned

The existing strong relationship with the policy stakeholder greatly facilitated the discussion to identify a dilemma. Nevertheless, busy schedules meant that there was a 6-week gap between a positive response to the proposal for additional data gathering, and the meeting to identify the dilemma. This delay, even given the strong existing relationship, underlines the practical challenges faced by policy stakeholders in collaborating in design processes.

3.2 GCS6 New Automotive step 1

Context

The New Automotive case study emerged from an alignment of interests identified through the personal networks of GREAT project partners. New Automotive need information about citizens' views on electric vehicles if they are to address their mission increase the pace of the shift to electric vehicles, and to influence policy development.

Activities

The proposal for the case study emerged from conversations between GREAT and Ben Nelmes, the CEO of New Automotive, and a public policy professional specialising in climate change and sustainability. The contacts were initiated by Baroness Briony Worthington, a collaborator of PlanetPlay and also an Executive Board member of New Automotive. A two hour zoom meeting was held involving Ben Nelmes and Baroness Worthington, Jude Ower (PlanetPlay) and Paul Hollins (Bolton). The remits and interests of the participants were discussed, and the possible collaborations using the GREAT infrastructure were explored. New Automotive expressed great interest, but no specific policy dilemma was identified to give a focus to the case study. It was agreed to follow up off-line, and to plan a second meeting to conduct more detailed planning. The GREAT team remained in touch with New Automotive to move forward, but the no specific commitments were achieved.

Results

There was a clear appetite for collaboration from New Automotive. They were impressed by the potential reach of PlanetPlay, as they are very reliant on data, and the approach offers large volumes of data. DiBL was seen as having value in identifying the issues, dilemmas and questions which are relevant to their stakeholders. There was discussion of involving a parliamentary working group that Baroness Briony Worthington participates in, but without any concrete commitment.

Lessons learned

Enthusiasm about proposed activities is a prerequisite for collaboration but is not in itself sufficient for reaching concrete proposals. Unstructured exploration of the potential for collaboration was the only approach which was feasible.

3.3 GCS7 Prosper step 1

Context

The Prosper case study was hosted by North-West University (NWU), a GREAT associate partner in South Africa. The case study addresses the need of the Department of Forestry, Fisheries and the Environment (DFFE) of South Africa, for reliable, up-to-date information on how citizens perceive and prioritize environmental challenges. An existing physical card game called 'Prosper', with an open license developed by NWU provided a solid starting point for design. The DiBL platform offered the possibility for wider reach, new forms of interaction, automated data capture and media prompts. These drivers aligned with NWU's interest in trialling self-directed learning activities with their student body.

Activities

Prof. Dorothy Laubscher of NWU is UNESCO Chair for Multimodal Learning and OER at NWU. Her UNESCO work opened connections with Department of Forestry, Fisheries and the Environment (DFFE). Initial conversations were positive, and a briefing pack was sent to the DFFE, with sample citizen-response dashboards. A meeting took place between ten representatives of the DFFE, NWU, and UNIR, at which the project was presented, and potential for collaboration was explored. This open-ended contact then evolved into efforts to draft a Memorandum of Understanding (MOU), which was a pre-condition for further collaboration.

The design constraints imposed by the DiBL platform were investigated, mapping the interactions of the existing Prosper card game against the features of DiBL, and considering the ambitions for enhanced game mechanics and data capture.

Results

Collaboration was established with the DFFE, who put forward a list of ten named individuals from DFFE who would be involved in the collaboration. However, the DFFE needed to formalise the collaboration through a detailed MOU before committing any staff time to workshops or data collection. Consequently, the GREAT team was frequently in the position of reaching out to the DFFE, while the DFFE was in the position that until the MOU was substantially agreed and routed for signature, the department simply could not engage in any substantive planning or scheduling, or

even engage in email exchanges. As a result, the DFFE were unable to participate in the definition of dilemmas, but they did make it clear that they were interested in how citizens viewed the SDGs and potential measures to address them. Accordingly, the two NWU designers mapped the existing Prosper OER card set onto climate-related SDGs. In NWU the ground was prepared for participation of students as respondents in the case study, with definition of expected insights and evidence.

It was concluded that the Prosper game could not adequately be transferred to the DIBL v1.0 platform. It was decided that development should wait until DIBL 2.0 was released, with the benefit that Prosper would be a good use case for finalisation of the feature set and validation of the release. This led to a 6-month delay.

Lessons learned

The concise presentation of the case study proposal to the DFFE was instrumental in obtaining their engagement, demonstrating respect for the Department's time constraints, but also gave them a tangible sense of value. However, alignment of interests and the commitment of individuals is not sufficient to generate collaboration with policy stakeholders. There are also administrative hurdles, which can create unanticipated delays. The enthusiasm of NWU and of the Prosper designers maintained momentum, despite this long hiatus.

3.4 GCS8, Play2Act2, step 1

Context

Play2Act is a large-scale digital study of climate engagement carried out with UNDP and integrated into games played globally. The first Play2Act case study, reported in D2.2, collected large volumes of high-quality data from participants in 183 countries. but lacked qualitative depth. Play2Act2 sought to strengthen the method used.

Activities

Informal contacts with UNDP made it clear that they had limited availability to participate in co-design activities at this stage of the case study, due to pressure of other commitments. They did, however, express their commitment to GREAT, and interest in the outcomes. Accordingly, initial design work was carried out in a meeting of GREAT partners UB, PlanetPlay and ZSI. An initial synchronous meeting was followed up with off-line exchanges using email, Teams and GoogleDocs. The starting point was documentation of gaps identified in the first iteration of Play2Act (see Annex 2, GCS8-Play2Act2_step-2_Gaps-identified-GCS5.pdf), which was updated. More generally, the strategy for the case study, and the requirements for its design, were

set out in a working document Advancing Play2Act: Why Future Iterations Matter (see Annex 2, GCS8-Play2Act2_step-1_Play2Act-Evolution.pdf).

Results

Given the limited availability of the policy stakeholder, it was decided to postpone formulation of a new question set. Rather, the focus would be on refinement of key questions for clarity and policy relevance, and on exploring methodological adjustments such as the inclusion of optional short free-text responses, randomisation of the order of questions and answers, and the testing different demographic question framings to improve inclusivity and reduce ambiguity.

Lessons learned

The continuity of an ongoing process can make discussions concrete and productive (in this case facilitated by the gap analysis from Play2Act1 and associated data. The step also showed that even when there is a well-established relationship with a policy stakeholder, unanticipated developments can disrupt the collaboration.

3.5 GCS9, Play2Act3, step 1

Context

This activity built on insights from Play2Act and Play2Act2, with a focus on balancing scientific rigour, institutional constraints (e.g., UNDP approval processes), and studio motivations. Design of the intervention was initiated early, to maximise the time available for planning and incorporating prior results.

Activities

UNDP were engaged in the conversation about setting the case study and made it clear that they were keen to be involved, with a maintained focus on the climate crisis, but they would not be able to collaborate further in this first step. Consequently, detailed planning was mainly within the GREAT project team, with scheduled and hoc planning meetings considering on how to build on the results of Play2Act2. Notes were taken and shared with the design team on the Google Drive.

It was noted that a GREAT public data workshop would soon take place within WP5. The purpose of this workshop was not to support design, but rather to involve citizens in interpreting the data that was generated by Play2Act1. However, the Play2Act3 design team felt that this public engagement would also be an opportunity to feed into the intervention, particularly as regards refinement of the thematic focus and identify gaps or emerging dilemmas.

Results

- Decision to integrate findings from the forthcoming WP5 data workshop into the design of Play2Act3,
- Agreement that Play2Act3 will test a fully revised question set, with stakeholder co-design incorporated earlier in the cycle than in previous iterations, to better align with the methodological goals of the GREAT project.
- A shortlist of potential policy dilemmas to explore was generated, alongside a preliminary list of stakeholders to consult during the next phase.

Lessons learned

The early start created a difficulty in that the results of Play2Act2 were not available to inform the discussions. In building on results involving multiple stakeholders there are dependencies that cannot be rushed.

3.6 GCS10 Beat the Heat, step 1

Context

Cyprus's national strategy for Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) is being implemented through the Whole School Approach supported by the Ministry of Education, Sports and Youth. It emphasizes the integration of sustainability principles across school culture, operations, curriculum, and community engagement. The goal is to embed environmental stewardship not just in what is taught, but in how schools function and engage with their wider communities. The Unit of Education for Environment and Sustainable Development (EESD), under the Cyprus Pedagogical Institute, supports national ESD implementation through teacher training, resource development, and school-wide capacity building. This task is challenging for the Ministry because it is not clear how the national strategy should be implemented in practice. Moreover, schools vary significantly in digital infrastructure and readiness for implementing game-based learning, and because educators lack guidance in translating systemic issues into student-friendly learning experiences. This setting creates a valuable opportunity to investigate how the aims of the ESD policy can be met in practice.

Activities

Two members of the EESD participated with the case study lead in a one-hour informal face to face meeting at the offices of the Cyprus Pedagogical Institute. The meeting was not recorded, but notes were taken and compiled into a PowerPoint presentation (see Annex 2, GCS10-Beat-the-Heat_step-1_presentation.pdf). The discussion was

focused and productive, aimed at aligning project objectives with national education priorities and confirming the case study sponsors commitment. Participants were introduced to the GREAT project, the DiBL platform, and the structure of the case study cycle.

Results

EESD agreed to support the study and emphasized that insights from the case study could feed into national policy development for Education for Sustainable Development (ESD). The policy is established, but it is not clear how it can best be implemented in teaching practice for climate change and sustainable development. A focus on provision for grade 6 students (age 11–12) was determined. Preliminary themes were proposed: The unit identified existing educational themes that could form the basis for a dilemma games, and as possible focuses for work in step 2:

- Natural Disasters
- Energy Audits
- Temperature Monitoring in Cyprus
- Sustainable School Spaces

It was decided to explore methods for implementing the policy by designing a dilemma game for primary education using the thematic areas above. To ensure alignment with the national curriculum and current reforms in primary education, teacher trainers will be involved in Stage 2 to co-design game components.

Lessons learned

The informal structure worked well and helped to generate enthusiasm. The meeting went into unexpected depth in the discussion of the collaboration, which the facilitator was able to deal with on-the-fly, drawing on her previous experience running a GREAT case study with a formal activity design. This step would have been hard to handle for a less experienced facilitator in the absence of a formal structure.

3.7 GCS11 DG ENER European Commission step 1

In response to guidance from the mid-term project review that an increased focus on Europe would be welcome, the GREAT team brainstormed themes which raise dilemmas for European policy. The chosen theme was housing, currently a burning issue in most member states. The team attempted to engage the European Parliament's Special Committee on the Housing Crisis in the European Union, established 18 December 2024. Unfortunately, emails to the members of the

Committee with a letter presenting the project and inviting collaboration did not receive a response. However, interest was raised in the European Commission, and an online meeting was organised with policy officers which suggested that collaboration in a PlanetPlay activity might be possible. A face-to-face meeting was scheduled to coincide with the EU cluster meeting in Brussels, but key stakeholders from the commission could not attend. Email follow-up did not succeed in building a viable collaboration, and the initiative was closed in September 2025, when it became too late to implement within the project lifespan. Thus, the project came close to establishing a case study, but, in the end, commitment was not achieved. The experience demonstrates that it is hard to get a collaboration onto the agenda of busy policy bodies, even when there is a clear and pressing policy dilemma. This is still more the case without a strong personal or institutional link into the organisation. Some initiatives will succeed, but it is to be expected that many will not.

3.8 Reflections on step 1 activities

Challenges in establishing collaboration with stakeholders and delays were a common theme throughout step 1 activities. An exception was Beat the Heat, where an alignment of interests, and strong personal connections, enabled progress to be made quickly. Collaboration was achieved, in all cases except for GCS11, but at the cost of adapting activities to reduce the degree of input required, with a concomitant additional complexity in the task of facilitators in planning and developing design work. The collaborations depended very much on individual personal or institutional contacts with stakeholders to establish commitment to joint work. Work involved small groups of representatives of policy stakeholders. In this step it was important to obtain input from a high level in the organisation, as a key output of this stage was the commitment of the organisation to participate in the study. In GCS2(b) Waterwise this involved the engagement of the Head of Membership, Marketing and Engagement, the Head of Commercial Services, and the Head of Policy and Research. In GCS9 Play2Act3 engagement was at the level of the Global Director of Climate Change. In contrast, in GCS10, Beat the Heat, while approval was an equally critical step, the process was simpler, as approval was at the level of the unit in the Ministry that was collaborating with GREAT. Until this commitment was obtained and people were tasked with working on the case study, detailed work could not progress. In some cases, this constrained collaboration, particularly with the lack of a MOU in GCS7, Prosper, and the difficulty of achieving commitment from stakeholders in GCS11 DG ENER.

4. Step two: game activity concepts

Step 2 builds on the design briefs developed in step 1 to determine what the game-based activities will achieve and how. Facilitators collaborate with stakeholders to define:

- Specific dilemmas that require information on citizens' preferences and attitudes which are of importance to the problem owner.
- The expected insight and evidence that can be offered to policymakers.
- The specific user groups who will be involved and their roles.
- How data will be gathered, analysed, and delivered to stakeholders.

These outcomes constitute a design challenge to be addressed in Step 3.

4.1 GCS2(b) Waterwise, step 2

Context

Step 1 identified a dilemma: There is a mismatch between public support for water re-use/harvesting and the building regulations. The regulations are currently under revision, but it is not clear what policies should be proposed.

The following questions were identified to move the design process forward:

- Is there clarity on what survey questions may inform policy interests?
- Is there a possibility to compare a normal survey format with a gamified one?
- Is there clarity on how the survey will connect or compliment the Waterwise DiBL work?
- What are the technical limitations of the survey format currently in use (this will inform the phrasing of survey questions)?

Activities

The activities focused on three key aspects: the survey content, whether some degree of gamification of the survey is appropriate, and a review of technical feasibility. Collaboration with Waterwise was limited by availability of Waterwise staff. Consequently, no synchronous activities took place with the case study sponsor, but they were updated by email. Design work was carried out by the GREAT team in synchronous and asynchronous meetings, maintaining contact with Waterwise by email to keep them updated on progress and receive input and feedback.

The Waterwise DiBL had highlighted a positive view of rainwater harvesting but participants could not articulate what this would look like. Input from Waterwise highlighted that new home building regulations are currently under discussion in the UK. Accordingly, there was a need to see if this positive reception would be maintained when the implementation and upkeep requirements of such systems were detailed to the public. Demographic questions should be used to see if surveying through a gaming community is effective at reaching a broad audience or not. The scope of the intervention will be limited to the UK.

It was decided not to pursue the playful/gamified within the detailed structure of the survey itself due to mixed results of a search of the literature on engagement through such mechanisms, and the advice of Professor Nic Whitton, external member of the Scientific Committee. In this way, the games-based aspect of the design remains the context of the activity in its embedding in a commercial game. The decision not to continue with a gamified survey approach confirmed the judgment of Griffiths et al. (2025) in their reflections on the Play2Act exploratory case study. An additional factor was the busy schedule of Waterwise, which meant that their availability for co-design would not be sufficient for a high-pressure design sprint at this late stage in the project. Time pressures were also an issue for the technical development work which would be required by PlanetPlay. Consequently, the study design will be shaped by both the agreed content and the constraints of the existing survey platform.

Results

Clarity was obtained on the design brief, including the strategy, scope and topic. The relevant building regulations were explored.

Lessons learned

The activities of step 2 and step 3 were hard to separate in practice, since (a) formulation of the finalised questions and delivery methods ran in parallel with the strategic decisions concerning a gamified approach, and (b) finalisation of the question set continued into step 3. This was in part a result of the extended time period required for consultations with the policy sponsor.

4.2 GCS6, New Automotive, step 2

Context

Positive contacts had been established with New Automotive in step 1, but the discussion had remained at a general level. Activities in this step aspired to

understanding the strategically significant issues and questions confronting New Automotive.

Activities

A meeting was arranged with Ben Nelmes of New Automotive, PlanetPlay and UB to define more specifically a policy dilemma (originally scheduled for step 1) and case study activities. The meeting was not recorded, but notes were taken. In the discussion, the underlying issue for New Automotive was how they could engage, specifically younger, citizens in debate about the transition to electric cars, highlighting perceived barriers that had emerged from their previous work:

- A lack of recharging infrastructure, and 'range fear' amongst potential purchasers.
- Cost, as electric vehicles are prohibitively expensive to younger consumers.
- The depreciation of the value of vehicles under ownership.

These concerns imply an overarching dilemma: that New Automotive needs to promote the switch to electric vehicles without having a clear picture of the concerns of the public which need to be addressed in the initiatives which they carry out. GREAT can contribute to achieving this understanding. New Automotive had been invited to extend their work to Germany, and they were keen to repeat the initiatives which had been successful in the UK, and to evaluate them in a new context.

New Automotive emphasised that any data collection in the case study should be fully compliant with their obligations under the relevant UK legislation, as non-compliance could threaten their NGO status. This was a motivation for them to be strongly engaged in the design of the intervention.

Results

A two-phase study was agreed, using DiBL platform with small stakeholder groups to establish key questions addressing the policy dilemma. The second phase would deploy the Planet Play Platform with geographically targeted groups in the UK and in Germany.

Lessons learned

Despite the progress made, the case study came to a half after step 2. The key reasons for this were:

1. **Availability of key personnel.** New Automotive, like most NGOs, is a small organisation, and a key participant was unavailable for an extended period. There was no spare capacity to pick up on this work.

2. **Changes in the policy context.** The policy environment was disrupted during steps 1 and 2 by the UK government's recent announcement of a delay in the complete phasing out of internal combustion vehicles until 2035, rather than 2030 as had been previously planned. This change was finally announced in January by the Department of transport of the UK (2024). Consequently the targets for the switch to electric vehicles became less pressing and New Automotive were on course at the time of steps 1 and 2. As a result, New Automotive was keen to gather new information to help them in their overall mission but did not have an immediately pressing policy issue which could facilitated the planning of the case study.
3. **Change in the scope of work.** During steps 1 and 2, New Automotive was given the opportunity to extend their work to Germany. This enhanced the European dimension of the work but also meant that the operating environment for New Automotive had been greatly expanded, with all the additional work and uncertainty that this implies.

4.3 GCS7, Prosper, step 2

Context

The case study had been delayed by the signature of a memorandum of understanding with the DFFE policy stakeholder, and by the need to postpone implementation until the release of DiBL 2.0 in December 2024.

Activities

The activities aimed to analyse the design of the Prosper card game and identify how it can incorporate elements of self-directed learning and games-based learning to

- facilitate an understanding of sustainable development,
- investigate how "Prosper" facilitates dialogue between students (future citizens) and policy stakeholders on sustainability issues.

The activities also determined the necessary modifications and adaptations to optimise Prosper for diverse educational contexts and student needs. In the absence of policy stakeholder engagement in the design, design activities involved telematic interactions between the NWU team and SGI, with documentation of the design brief in an online spreadsheet.

Results

The focus on the Sustainable Development Goals was defined, in line with the indications received from the DFFE in step 1. Game activities were designed, incorporating a teams-based approach and new solution cards. Content relating to sustainable development was created, covering a wide range of topics (environment, social, economic, etc.). A detailed design brief was prepared, with the structure of the game, and procedures for each round of play (see Annex 2, GCS7-Prosper_step-2_simulation-sheet.xlsx).

Lessons learned

Given the impossibility of engaging the policy stakeholder in design activities, the project had to decide whether to abandon the case study or to press ahead on the basis of the indications which had been received in step 1. Informal contacts suggested that DFFE were still interested in the results, and that it worth persevering. While this was not ideal, the commitment of the NWU designers to the SDG theme made this a viable strategy. The live online Excel plotting sheet worked well, as the NWU and SGI collaborators could sequentially plan and design the problem and solution cards, where the SGI team could provide feedback comments for specific content that needed clarity or updating.

4.4 GCS8, Play2Act2, step 2

Context

Methodological adjustments were proposed in step 1 (optional short free text responses and testing of different demographic question framings to improve inclusivity and reduce ambiguity). This step sought to specify which changes would be made and how, and to agree on a question set.

Activities

UNDP clarified that they could not endorse any new question sets without a formal approval process, and the timeline did not allow sufficient time for this. As a result, the plan was adapted, seeking to maintain the methodological value of the case study. Meetings were held of the core research team from UB, PlanetPlay and ZSI, followed by consultations with the wider project team to obtain feedback.

Results

The approach suggested in step 1 was confirmed and elaborated, using the existing question set. Planned methodological enhancements included (a) free-text responses for richer qualitative data, (b) two studio-customised questions per deployment to support studio engagement and co-design, (c) randomisation of answer order for

methodological testing. Play2Act2 was repositioned as a smaller-scale refinement phase, and the new question set originally planned for Play2Act2 was deferred to a later iteration, Play2Act3, giving time for UNDP approval and data-informed refinement.

Lessons learned

However solid a collaboration with a policy stakeholder may be, unanticipated developments in schedules and processes can disrupt the collaborative design of interventions. In this case, creative thinking is needed about what can be learned from the study.

4.5 GCS9, Play2Act3, step 2

Context

In step 1, the initial framing of the case study design was carried out by the GREAT team, because UNDP staff were unable to participate in the period from May to September. As a result, there was a hiatus before the start of step 2. It was important to engage UNDP policy and communications specialists in shaping the intervention, to ensure global acceptability, alignment with institutional standards, and suitability for co-branding and dissemination.

Activities

In step 1 it was decided to make use of the results of a public data workshop organised by WP5 to feed into the design activities in step 2. The data workshop took place in June 2025 and is described in *D5.3 Final impact assessment report*, but unfortunately only 3 of the 100 participants who had agreed to take part actually attended the workshops. This participation was too low to generate a useable input to the design process. As reported in D5.3, a second workshop was organised with a higher participation rate, but this was too late to be relevant to Play2Act3. As a fall, back the question set was based on an analysis Play2Act1, which had been prepared as an input to the revision of the question set in Play2Act2, but could not be used because UNDP were not able to approve any substantial changes. The project team did initial drafting and shared this with UNDP for an iterative process of review, feedback and revision. The question “I trust my national government to act on climate change” was removed because UNDP was concerned about its political sensitivity. Once agreement was arrived at on all open issues, a final document was shared with UNDP for formal approval, which was obtained.

The design was longer than previous surveys, to test the balance between richness of data and response rate. It included free text responses as an optional field following selected Likert scale questions, and the opportunity for studios to define two questions of their own. This required new functionality to be implemented in the PlanetPlay system.

Results

The output of this step was the formal approval from UNDP of a question set to be implemented in step 3 (see Annex 2, GCS9-Play2Act3_step-2_Survey-Content.pdf), and agreed requirements for new functionality to be included in the app.

Lessons learned

An unexpectedly low level of participation in the first WP5 public data workshop meant that this event could not provide input to the design of Play2Act3. Having to hand a detailed analysis of how to build on the question set from Play2Act1 enabled the project to move forward with a revised strategy and showed the value of having a rigorous review at the end of a case study. The design of an inquiry can be politically sensitive in ways which are not foreseen by researchers.

4.6 GCS10, Beat the Heat

Context

During stage 1, the case study sponsor suggested a list of pre-existing climate change topics that the case study focus on. These included: Natural Disasters; Energy Audit; Temperatures in Cyprus; Sustainable Spaces and Green Infrastructure. These suggestions informed the protocol for Step 2a and the activity design (see Annex 2, GCS10-Beat-the-Heat_step-2_session-guiding questions_March 2025.pdf)

Activities

Two Zoom activities were conducted. The first involved six members of the EESD, and one from the Cyprus Energy Agency. It lasted two hours and focused on game concepts based on green infrastructure. The meeting was facilitated by Anna Merry (FU) and Jo Bech Dalsgaard (SGI). It was planned to record the meeting on a Miro board, but the participants were not comfortable to do this while discussing, and so the transcript provides better documentation. Discussions covered the use of technical tools in schools, shortcomings in technical infrastructure, and alignment with policy. The session concluded with a consensus on developing a shorter, modular game prototype, preparing independent technical resources for pilots and gathering structured feedback from educators before full integration.

The second activity, including 3 members of EESD, reflected SGI's view that the subject needed to be further narrowed down to achieve a viable design brief. It was proposed to use thermal images to explore students' understanding and prompt ideas for improvements using green infrastructure. It was agreed to include small dilemmas (e.g. "You want to play outside but it's too hot, what would you do?"), followed by possible votes on solutions, or points for innovation. It was suggested that there should be a link to physical activity outdoors, with thematic questions explored in DiBL.

Results

The activities were documented in a summary and a transcript. A description of the game to be designed was generated: modular, short (e.g. 10 minutes), with age-appropriate content based on visual prompts. Shortcomings in technical infrastructure led to a decision to support team participation with a single device. A theme was identified: urban temperature and outdoor comfort, with an emphasis on green infrastructure for cooling. It was agreed to The Cyprus Energy Agency's agreed to review all materials and ensure alignment with policy goals and factual correctness. One possibility moving forward is an alignment with the EU Climate Pact, which will be discussed again at a later date at the stage of project dissemination.

Lessons learned

Ice breakers were an important first step in the meetings. The mix of educators and subject specialists generated dynamic and insightful conversations. Practical examples of games and initiatives helped to spark conversation. Feedback from players of the Green Roof game was a valuable input. Structured facilitation led to clear outcomes. Challenges were identified for this context, primarily the limited technical infrastructure and open questions about how the game would align with curricula and policy requirements.

4.7 Reflections on step 2 activities

All the case studies, apart from GCS10 Beat the Heat, experienced constraints on the availability of policy stakeholders for design collaborations to some degree. The reasons for this ranged from institutional schedules (GCS2 and GCS8), availability of key personnel and changed policy environment (GCS6), formal constraints on collaboration pending a memorandum of understanding (GCS7). All the case studies managed to find strategies to overcome these challenges, except for New Automotive, which was terminated. Typically, these involved the exchange of drafts online, feedback in comments in shared documents and email exchanges, supplemented by occasional synchronous conversations. These strategies inevitably reduced the

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richness of the design process compared with that which had been anticipated and moved them away from truly collaborative design towards a consultancy model.

5. Step three: collaborate in design of game activities

This step concerns design of interaction and interface in the games-based activities, linking the design ideas of stakeholders with the project technical team, as regards:

- Gameplay interaction design.
- Interface design.
- Content selection and design.

The wireframes which emerge from this process are passed to WP3 for implementation and delivery.

5.1 GCS2(b) Waterwise, step 3

Context

As noted in GCS2(b) Waterwise step 2, above, steps 2 and 3 overlapped, and were also carried out by the same participants. Consequently, the design brief was not formalised but consisted of the requirement to create a survey to be delivered in a commercial game, in the UK, to obtain information on gamers' views on the practical implementation of water harvesting systems in new homes. This will provide data to inform the position of Waterwise on policy relating to water harvesting building regulations, currently under review in the UK.

Activities

A meeting of UB and PlanetPlay was held on 25th September to plan the practicalities of implementation which constrain the design and its scheduling. Building on this base line, and the design brief from Step 2, design work was carried out in living documents shared between a team drawn from project partners UB (case study lead), ZSI (evaluation), PlanetPlay (technical infrastructure) and UNIR (WP2 leaders). The documents were also shared with Waterwise, and input was provided by the Waterwise Head of Policy and Research and a colleague on the emerging survey questions and strategy (see Annex 2, GCS2b-Waterwise_step3_PlanetPlay-survey-design_V.1.pdf).

In parallel with this process, PlanetPlay made contact with 70 game studios who might be willing to collaborate in the delivery of the survey. Particular efforts were made to

build on contacts with studios who had expressed interest in participating in earlier case studies. A major studio with very substantial reach initially agreed to embed the app in-game, but in the end the studio withdrew. The GREAT team then sought alternative channels to the players. At the time of reporting this work is still underway.

Results

A living document was developed with draft survey questions, with comments from two members of Waterwise, followed up by email. On the basis of this result, the final design was created by the GREAT project team and shared with Waterwise for feedback. The pragmatic decision was taken not to implement any new functionality for the survey at this late stage in the project. The collaboration with game studios has not yet been finalised in agreement to embed the inquiry.

Lessons learned

As noted in Step 2 above, the activities of Step 2 and Step 3 were hard to separate in practice. A survey intervention was developed, with the support and collaboration of the policy stakeholder (even though this collaboration was limited by availability). This showed that building on the outputs of a DiBL intervention to design a more focused and quantitative inquiry is a strategy which is practicable and is of interest to policy stakeholders. While the policy stakeholder was committed to the inquiry, and keen to be involved, the practicalities of availability of personnel meant that their participation was limited to providing feedback on proposals prepared by the project team.

Obtaining the agreement of game studios is a delicate task, depending on excellent relations with the studio, and an understanding of the studio's motivations and concerns. Even if these conditions are in place, internal changes in the studio can lead to non-engagement in particular instances.

5.2 GCS7, Prosper, step 3

Context

Step 2 produced a detailed outline of gameplay. In step 3 the design of the game itself was carried out, including the interface and finalised content relating to the SDGs. Engagement from the policy stakeholder was minimal in the first two steps, due to delays in signing of a required memorandum of understanding.

Activities

The policy stakeholder (DFFE) was still unable to participate in activities, as the necessary Memorandum of Understanding had not yet been approved and so the initial agreed requirement from step 1, to stimulate reflection and discussion on the SDGs was maintained. Strong collaboration was established in step 2 between the NWU and SGI collaborators and this will be built on in step 3. The live Excel spreadsheet which was used in Step 2 to document the game play fed into the design activities, represented in a Miro wireframe (see Annex 2, GCS7-Prosper_step-3_game-flow-Miro.pdf). Problem cards, solution cards, team structures, and scoring mechanisms were all defined (see Annex 2, GCS7-Prosper_step-3_Content-for-DiBL_map-to-new-scoring-system.xlsx).

In the playtest, Prosper DiBL's briefing-play-reflection loop kept participants interested but exposed friction points: players wanted clearer success criteria, more visible links between SDG icons, individual/team/world scores, and their chosen cards, as well as crisper guidance on when reflection occurs. Interface issues—uncertain click targets, QR-code logins, off-screen images, mismatched card sizes, and the awkward Zoom-plus-phone setup—slowed play, while the absence of feedback in round 2 felt like a glitch. Testers recommended concrete, persistent team identities (e.g., scientists, NGOs) tied to distinct card decks, a prominent "Choose" button, richer facilitator screens showing all team names and scores, and a quicker start with less facilitator narration so teams can discuss and present their own choices. Addressing these clarity, UI, and facilitation tweaks should streamline future sessions without changing the engaging core mechanics.

Constant communication was maintained between NWU and SGI. The feedback from the GREAT project case study leaders was invaluable, and the results of the play-test evaluation led to an additional round of implementation work. The development team stayed in close communication with the NWU staff responsible for implementation. Prof. Deon van Tonder, director for the module that the Prosper DiBL will be used in, worked in parallel with the development work in determining timeframes for the data collection. Mr. Ike Mabelebele, junior lecturer who was to facilitate Prosper activities throughout the intervention (accompanied by Byron Bunt), was trained as facilitator.

Results

The basic structure of the Prosper DiBL that was eventually released on version 2.0 is identical to that proposed in step 2. Step 3 translated that structure into DiBL 2.0, and designed the interface, implemented the new scoring system and worked on the visual design of the game (presentation of the cards and SDG icons etc.). The result was a

fully featured Prosper DiBL ready for deployment. Figure 3 below shows a player’s mobile screen with a player’s choice on policy to address plastic choked oceans, and the facilitators screen showing an overview of the deliberations of the different groups.

Figure 2: Prosper DiBL player and facilitator screens

Lessons learned

The DiBL 2.0 release provided all the functionality that was required for implementation of the game. Miro proved to be an effective tool for the representation of the design. The evaluation of the prototype was very valuable in informing the design of the version delivered to step 4. Feedback from the GREAT project case study leaders and from the playtest were invaluable in refining the design of the DiBL Prosper game. A reflection is that the description of step 3 in the methodology assumes that implementation will be carried out independently of design of the wireframes. However, the rapid pace of development enabled the process to be much more iterative. The Miro board functioned both as a place where the required functionality could be specified, and as a representation of the developing structure of the game.

5.3 GCS8, Play2Act2, step 3

Context

A set of methodological changes was defined in step 2, to be included in the PlanetPlay survey app.

Activities

The agreed changes from step 2 were designed in the PlanetPlay survey app (optional free text responses, randomisation of button order, studio defined questions). Redesign was carried out in response to internal feedback, to ensure that free text fields look like an opportunity to enter text. The style of borders and colours were maintained. A placeholder text was added, but the back end ensures that it does not bias the answer.

PlanetPlay contacted studios on their list of studios engaged during the duration of GREAT and held a series of one-to-one and group calls with each participating studio to review question ideas, provide feedback, and align phrasing with Play2Act2's policy focus. Two forms of reaching players were discussed, (a) in game placement (in which the PlanetPlay survey app is embedded in a game with a hyperlink), and (b) player media channels (in which the messaging and social media accounts managed by games studios are used to directly reach their players).

Parallel discussions with UNDP clarified the distinction between 'core questions' (researcher-authored) and 'custom questions' (studio-authored) and confirmed that UNDP branding could remain.

Results

A redesigned PlanetPlay survey app with detailed planning of features. Agreement with studios to support the intervention:

- Sybo: Subway Surfers (in-game placement, player media channels)
- TenSquare: Fishing Clash (in-game placement, player media channels)
- Funplus: (player media channels)

Only one studio, Sybo, took up the option of including their own questions, but they were very enthusiastic about the opportunity.

Figure 3: PlanetPlay survey app and multiple choice question

Lessons learned

The design decisions required implementation changes. A survey generates a certain number of pages and at the end it links back to the landing page. With optional studio questions, the number of pages can vary, resulting in different numbers of questions per publisher per game, and pushing beyond what might normally be expected in a survey. The current system expects a fixed number of pages. A short-term solution was to duplicate the survey for each instantiation and give it a new name. The iterations themselves ensure that the data is correctly stored. Other studios wanted to link back to their game at the end, not to the landing page of the case study.

5.4 GCS9, Play2Act3, step 3

Context

In step 2, studios did not participate in refining question content. In step 3 they were expected to take on a key role in determining the delivery of the survey, and in developing studio-authored custom questions.

Activities

Studios have been invited to collaborate authoring additional custom questions, embedding the PlanetPlay app which delivers the survey on their platforms, and preparing promotional messages to accompany the survey in their respective platforms. In parallel agreement to embed the app in games is being sought through conversations with individual studios conducted by PlanetPlay staff. An innovation in this step was the use of a team of four to initiate contacts with studios and to manage

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subsequent communications, a task which had previously been carried out by a single person. To maintain consistent communications, a studio briefing sheet was prepared with richer content which gave a fuller picture of the interactions in the survey to be embedded. 70 studios were contacted, making use of a list of studios who have been engaged in the project, or in communication with it. The list is maintained by partner PlanetPlay and provided a means of coordinating the work of the team of four. These activities are underway at the time of writing this report.

Results and Lessons learned

At the time of writing, work on GCS9, Play2Act, step 3 is underway, and it is too soon to provide the results. However, some lessons learned have become clear. Initial results on the authoring of custom questions are not encouraging because none have yet been submitted by studios. The task of agreeing placement of the survey app in games is also proving more challenging than anticipated, reflecting the retrenchment of the games industry in the face of a downturn in the sector, and high levels of churn and redundancies requiring new relationships to be established with employees who may be concerned about taking risks which might undermine their job security. It is also possible that there is a degree of fatigue among studios who have received multiple requests for collaboration from GREAT. Feedback from studios suggests that yearly participation in such initiatives is an appropriate rhythm. The fraught political environment may also be a factor in discouraging any collaboration which might be seen to have political overtones.

While the use of a four-person team to contact the entire list of studios has increased bandwidth, there is an overhead of coordination potential lapses in communication. A structured workflow might be valuable in this respect.

5.5 GCS10, Beat the Heat, step 3

Context

The design brief developed in stage defined a dilemma game and associated workshop(s) aims to raise awareness of passive cooling strategies and empower youth to imagine climate-resilient futures for their schools and public spaces. This will engage students in the reform of schools in Cyprus under the whole school approach policy and generate active dialogue with policy makers.

Activities

It was intended to hold a design workshop with all stakeholders, but holidays in Cyprus made this impossible to schedule. Accordingly, the activities were split in two. The first

meeting involved a representative of the Cyprus Energy Agency (CEA) and the GREAT design team. CEA was a crucial stakeholder at this point, providing subject area knowledge and access to game content materials (see Annex 2, GCS10-Beat-the-Heat_step-3_game-material-from- CEA.pdf).

Figure 4: Heatmap of a rooftop, provided by the Cyprus Energy Agency

The Discussions were focused on the structure of the activity, the integration of data and visualizations into the DiBL tool, and how to effectively localize game content.

A co-creation and testing session was organised to test and refine a prototype design. This involved representatives from the Unit of Education for the Environment and Sustainable Development (EESD) of the Cyprus Ministry of Education, including teacher trainers and educators, who are the case study sponsors and who supported the pilot phase. Participants interacted directly with the digital game via the DiBL platform in both teacher and student roles. Stakeholders provided practical feedback, including how to simplify technical content, clarify instructions, and ensure visual materials were age-appropriate and locally relevant. Additional emphasis was placed on ensuring the game could align with the national ESD curriculum and be used as a tool to support teachers' reflective practice.

Results

From the first session, a document was developed to represent the detailed game flow (see Annex 2, GCS10-Beat-The-Heat_step-3_full-case.pdf), and a facilitator overview (see Annex 2, GCS10-Beat-the-Heat_step-3_facilitator-overview.jpg). This was then implemented in DiBL in an agile process which overlapped with step 4 of the case study cycle, and feedback obtained at a meeting with stakeholders (see Annex 2, GCS10-Beat-the-Heat_stakeholder-feedback-presentation.pdf). This session validated the game structure, confirmed its suitability for the target players, and identified key adjustments required prior to piloting. The structure of the pilot

activities was agreed. A demo of the final game design is available here:
<https://web.dibl.eu/caseview/8160?autostart>

Figure 5: Joining screen of Beat the Heat

Lessons learned

The structured walkthrough of the five-part activity design, shared with the Cyprus Energy Agency in the first meeting, was effective in guiding discussion. The agile development of a prototype game in step 3 enabled the stakeholders to engage directly with the game, and to provide more effective feedback and guidance.

5.6 Reflections on step 3

All the case studies succeeded in designing interventions which could be delivered to citizens to gather their views. In all cases this was with the collaboration of stakeholders, even if in some cases this was limited to feedback on drafts, and the approval of the final designs. An exception was GCS7, in which the DFFE was forced to take a hands-off stance because of the difficulties in signing a memorandum of understanding. The project persisted with this collaboration because a clear focus had been established in step 1, and it was clear that the DFFE were interested in the results. Indeed, a memorandum of understanding was eventually signed after the end of the design steps.

However, despite reaching successful conclusions, the challenges raised by restricted availability of policy stakeholders for collaborative activities from steps 1 and 2 remained present in step 3, although the feedback from UNDP in GCS8 increased in comparison to step 2. In those case studies where collaboration was low, the team

found ways forward to maintain engagement and updates through asynchronous channels.

On the other hand, engagement with policy stakeholders in GCS2 Waterwise remained solid, even if with a small team, and engagement with the Cyprus Ministry of Education was strong in GCS10.

Collaboration with game studios in engaging their players with the GREAT PlanetPlay survey app became an important aspect of work, with extended conversations being conducted with multiple studios through remote meetings, face-to-face meetings (particularly making use of opportunities at events), and email. A list of studio contacts has been managed by PlanetPlay throughout duration of the project, and it now includes some 70 studios. This, and participation in events, has been the basis for approximately 200 individual conversations with game studios during 2025 seeking to engage them in project activities. Communication with studios was also managed by a team of four, rather than a single person as was previously the case. Despite these intensive efforts, it proved harder to engage studios that in 2024. This is ascribed to the increasingly challenging environment in the industry with extensive layoffs, which increased dramatically in 2024, as summarised by Robinson et al. (2024)

In 2023 and 2024 the game industry has seen an unprecedented wave of layoffs and closures. Publishers cancelled projects en masse, downsized studios, or downright closed them regardless of venerated history or recent pedigree. In 2023, about 10.000 jobs were eradicated; by just May 2024, this tally had doubled. <https://dl.acm.org/doi/pdf/10.1145/3665463.3678861>

This trend continues in 2025, as monitored by Knezovic (2025) of the mobile advertising company Udonis, which describes the situation as 'bleak' and 'just as brutal as the last two years, if not worse'. Similarly, a report by the Games Developers Conference (2025) estimates that one in ten developers have been made redundant in the past year. In addition to the loss of established contacts through redundancy, the associated organisation restructuring often means that responsibility for collaboration is passed to a new person. It is also possible that the fraught political environment is discouraging stakeholders from participating in any initiative which could be seen as politically delicate. Another possible factor is that some studios have reached a temporary limit in their capacity to collaborate, and that less frequent requests would be more effective, and indeed the studio which has carried most GREAT interventions has suggested that a yearly rhythm would be the most appropriate.

5.7 Redesign of technical support for step 3 PlanetPlay activities

An additional outcome from step 3 has been the redesign of the PlanetPlay publishing process. Experience from step 3 PlanetPlay activities across the case studies showed that the process of creating and configuring a link to be embedded in a commercial game was difficult for non-experts to understand, and was highly dependent on expert technical support, which only one person could provide. A particular issue was the need to ensure that the data gathered by the survey app was correctly stored in the database, specifying a source, and a distribution with the name of the studio and the distribution in-game. In the past, this has been dependent on an expert designing a custom link for each game studio involved on a local machine, with the knowledge of exactly how the links should be formed.

In PlayToAct2, the more ambitious design process meant that more people were involved in talking to publishers, creating a danger that the final deployment might not be correctly configured. This was a risk factor and also created barriers to collaborative design. In response to this challenge, a Content Management System (CMS) was created by PlanetPlay. The new CMS enables the process to be decentralised on the web. It handles all the unique links for the various places in their platforms where game studios promote surveys. The administrator can "Copy this link over", for a particular survey and partner under specific circumstances ensuring that the correct link is deployed to launch the app. In the CMS there is a 'deploy' button, and once the environment has been defined, it can be live within minutes. Because of this, in Play2Act2, a non-expert was able to coordinate with the TenSquare studio, and send the links directly, facilitating the embedding without extensive consultation.

However, the less technical the administrators, the more safeguards are needed. JSON is used to manage the nested sets of data, with protection against editing and saving changes to a live survey, providing insurance against configuration problems. It is also possible to validate surveys, and to check that the configurations are consistent in data reporting, and that all options are consistent. If everything is green, then it is ready to publish.

The system is based on a configuration format that specifies multiple locales (i.e. translated languages) and that certain questions have certain settings, for example to enable or disable randomization, or to add a question only be answerable with a free form text box. These decisions can be applied on a per language basis as well, although realistically multiple-choice questions will be the same in all languages. This approach makes it much easier to change the design at the last-minute in response to feedback

from designers or users. The CMS also tracks additional metadata, recording everything that was previously tracked in a spreadsheet. For example, the CMS shows:

- the start date
- the status
- if a screenshot of the live implementation is available
- language localisation
- social media posts.

If a studio wants to link back to their game after the player finishes the survey, rather than landing page, this can be set up in the CMS. The studios who have been contacted are also recorded. A medium term goal is to have some of this information in a persistent unique URL, avoiding the need to copy and paste links back to a studio. With this link, the studio will be able to see everything that has been currently agreed on, and if another game title is added later, the same web page will still show the current links.

The CMS runs in the cloud and is based on Payload TMS. Only a privileged user can deploy to production, but there is sufficient granularity in the permission model to handle dozens or hundreds of surveys. There are some workflow features building on experience of implementing the case studies. For example, a translation can be triggered, and the Google translation API is used to translate the text, which is pushed to a spreadsheet so that other people can work on it.

Since the completion of Play2Act2, the CMS has been extended to enable administrators to quickly look at the responses coming in, to ensure that the system is not accidentally configured in a way which suppresses responses to certain questions, or that no text responses are being received. It is obvious at a glance that every question is generating data, and the engagement rates are shown for particular countries. In principle, this makes it possible for remedial design activities to be undertaken should there be a need. However, studios usually run for a week, as did SYBO in this case study, and it would not make sense to change or stop the process. The benefits are more about quality assurance and understanding the effectiveness of the design. For example, it became clear that Iran had a very low completion rate, suggesting a need to localise the language in future. Similarly, when it became clear that many people from Poland were engaged, that suggested that Polish should be included. Because the translations are AI generated and then checked, these changes could in theory be implemented on the fly.

Access to live data was also valuable. A spreadsheet version of the responses was easily made by the administrator, and translated, highlighting the ones that had a certain length and then shared with the marketing department. This makes it easy to find quotes from players for a press by the project or by the studios. This live data also provides immediate feedback on design decisions. For example, there was a concern that free text questions might generate spam, or customer support queries from players. But on deployment, the new CMS made it obvious that the majority of the text responses, probably 90% plus, were legitimate people commenting, even if some texts were short or negative.

6. Interviews with stakeholders

On reviewing the work reported above, a clear theme emerges of low levels of availability of policy stakeholders for collaboration in design activities, raising questions about the degree to which the project was of value to them. Between May and November 2025 interviews were carried out with eight stakeholders to explore this, plus an interview with two members of partner PlanetPlay and one in WP5 with the policy stakeholder from GCS3. This corpus of text is too extensive to analyse in detail here, and it will form the basis of a project publication. One interviewee was unable to provide approval of the use of quotations in time for this deliverable, and so their transcript has not been taken into consideration here. However, extracts from the interviews show the stakeholders' perception of the benefits of the interventions, and their collaboration. These are expanded on in the conclusions, below.

As regards the policy stakeholders. (Interviewers' speech is in parenthesis).

Benefits: All the five policy stakeholders interviewed said that their participation had brought benefits to their organisation.

- Chiara Cardelli, Klimafons: "...totally new for me was the thing with the reward or competition ... there were also aspects I hadn't considered before. ...it's also interesting to see which suggestions the students liked the most there were also several new ideas that can be taken from this ... not just for this campaign."
- Marina Kyriakou, Urban Gorillas: "...we reached out to a different audience than we would if we were trying on our own." "... an easy and very efficient way to make people talk about this topic." "... we had several different groups engaging in discussion of the topic of green roofs in the Cypriot context ... that is a very good positive thing. ... people were looking at this solution in a very enthusiastic way."

- Marios Antoniou, Cyprus Ministry of Education. "... if you have a dilemma, ... it gives people the opportunity to do some deep thinking. ... to also practise the skills of being informed, so you would do research. You would try, hopefully to see all things consider and hear different views and opinions and also practise using your critical thinking skills. And that's a very good added value of this project..." "a very important goal that we want to promote is sustainability citizenship. ... I think that this is a very good tool."
- Sylvia Tovar Jardon, UNDP: "... we were happy and quite impressed by the results of the reach. ... the number of countries where players were responding from was quite impressive."

Collaboration: The stakeholders felt that this had been achieved and valued it.

- Marina Kyriakou, Urban Gorillas: "we felt very welcomed and appreciated. Having a say is important because in the end we can also get the results that we want."
- Marios Antoniou, Cyprus Ministry of Education: "... there was a lot of feedback that changed things to a big extent" "... when you have something that is created in a collaborative manner, you will have more things that come into the design process and make hopefully at the end of the day a better product."
- Silvia Tovar Jardon, UNDP: "We were strongly involved in the design of the survey ... We really appreciated that".

Time was a common constraint, both through individual availability and institutional processes. To these can be added the lengthy delays in signature of a MOU in GCS7.

- Marina Kyriakou, Urban Gorillas: "The timing for was not perfect for me, but otherwise maybe" (would have had more time to be involved).
- Silvia Tovar Jardon, UNDP: "... we agreed ... on a work plan that was very difficult to comply with because of our internal requirements or processes".

Wider collaboration was cautiously welcomed but not seen as practicable.

- Marina Kyriakou, Urban Gorillas: "... this collaboration ... gave us the opportunity to think ... about how to involve the stakeholders that are responsible for this, everyone: planners, architects, people in residents' committees. ... if it was a project that had more duration, maybe it would have been possible, if we had more time and more resources to do that. ... it's difficult to have commitment

from people who are not paid to do this or cannot allocate time.” “We invested the time that we thought we could invest, but if we were more directly in the project then of course everything could have been even more.”

- Silvia Tovar Jardon, UNDP: “Bringing in other actors could have enhanced the survey, probably. ... I’m not sure if in this particular initiative it should have been the way forward ... for us it was very important that certain games, and the great academics, were involved...”
- Marios Antoniou, Cyprus Ministry of Education: (you didn't feel the need for any additional participants) “I think it will be the next phase, the pilot phase where the participants will receive the feedback of teachers.”

As regards the games studios

Benefits. There is a substantial group of games studios that sees benefits in collaborating with GREAT.

- Mathias Norvig, Sybo: “I like the idea that we can put purpose into the game, and that we can do things with the game, so we want to try as many initiatives as possible and also see what resonates with the players.”
- Amit Khanduja, Reliance: “There is no direct ROI ... But we believe in purpose-driven storytelling where we are able to educate and inspire, or raise awareness with our games.”
- Eight game studio representatives in the GREAT session at Climate Week in New York expressed their organisations openness to considering collaborations of the sort offered by GREAT.

Collaboration. Interviewees saw collaboration in terms of alignment of interests.

- Mathias Norvig, Sybo: “anything that touches the game that is risky. I'm happy if we can spearhead some of the change and show the studios that are hesitant that this is not killing that game.”
- Amit Khanduja, Reliance: “I think every studio to some extent is doing something or other, it is just how you align with their corporate mission that makes it easier from that perspective.”

Constraints on collaboration. The interviewees saw control on player experience as an absolute requirement. This means that interactions that happen on their platform cannot be collaboratively designed.

- Mathias Norvig, Sybo: "...anything that takes you as a player out of the game experience ... there is a risk that they don't come back, simply because they are jumping down another rabbit hole."
- Amit Khanduja, Reliance: "One of the biggest factors is retention and engagement. After we launch a survey, I don't want a lot of our players walking away, or losing them just because they did not want to do a survey."

7. Conclusions

The GREAT project explores how games-based activities can provide insight into citizens views, through between policymakers, games companies and academic researchers. Within this context WP2 is tasked with (a) grounding project activities in authentic dilemmas, and (b) producing specifications and design documents which enable the case studies to be implemented with citizens. Ultimately these activities contribute to the two overarching project objectives:

- To understand how games-based activities can be designed to provide a link between citizens and policy makers.
- To understand the benefits and risks to citizens, policy stakeholders and policy makers, of using games-based activities as a link between citizens and policy makers.

In this final WP2 deliverable it is appropriate to reflect on what has been learned which contributes to the projects understanding of these objectives, and to the wider project research questions.

7.1 Collaboration with stakeholders

A key feature of GREAT is that the consortium does not include any policymakers, and only one games company (SGI focusing on serious games) and one company focusing on the information flows between games studios and policymakers (PlanetPlay). This structure of the consortium was designed to ensure that the activities carried out with policymakers and games studios are authentic, in that they respond to real-world needs, rather than the simply fulfilling the targets of a funded project. In the activities of WP2 we have endeavoured to engage policy stakeholders and game studios in designing interventions, and in so doing we have gained insight both into how to do this most effectively (objective 1) and into the benefits concerns and risks of stakeholders which enable and constrain these collaborations (objective 2).

The workplan of GREAT tested the proposition that the services offered by the project would be so compelling that stakeholders would be motivated to contribute their effort to collaborations in the design and execution of case studies. WP2 has shown this to be true, by designing a successful programme of case studies in collaboration with policy stakeholders and game studios. In doing so, it has fulfilled its objectives, i.e. (1) to ground project activities in authentic policy dilemmas, in actual challenges of social participation, and in the needs of policy makers, and (2) to produce specifications and design documents. Over the period of the project there has been substantial collaboration from policy stakeholders, with 102 participations of policy stakeholders across the wide range of collaborative design sessions carried out (21 in year 1, 40 in year 2, and 41 in year 3). Nevertheless, it should be recognised that this collaboration has been less intensive than had been hoped for.

Collaborations with game studios have been successful. As foreseen in the DoA, this collaboration mainly involved activities leading to agreement to obtain access to players for a particular case study, on the appropriate channels. To this was added the inclusion of custom studio-defined questions within the PlanetPlay app, and the design of the flow of the survey app (primarily how the player was returned to the host game). These activities took place in step three, so the number of collaborations with studios was limited by the termination of two case studies before they reached step 3, both of which would have involved studios. Throughout the project a list of studios interested in collaboration with GREAT has been compiled and managed. By the end of project this had reached 70 studios who were briefed when opportunities arose. However the dire economic environment faced by studios, described in section 5.6 above, has made engagement with studios an increasingly demanding task.

Benefits and risks

GREAT research question RQ 2.2 ask “What are the benefits and risks to policy makers and policy stakeholders of using games-based activities to elicit, represent and communicate citizens’ views on policy dilemmas?”, and the results of WP2 are very relevant to this.

While the collaborations conducted by WP2 have been successful in reaching their operational objectives, the intensity of collaboration with policy stakeholders has been lower than hoped for. This raises the question of whether this reflects a lack of perceived value in the GREAT model, and/or if there were barriers to collaboration. To this end, WP2 carried out a series of interviews, summarised in section 6, above, with statements made relating to the benefits of case studies and nature of the

collaboration. These showed that, on the contrary, all interviewees experienced benefits from their participation in GREAT, and highly valued the data generated and the process which led to it. This was clearly not the reason for the challenges experienced in achieving collaboration. What then was the explanation for the limited range of collaboration?

Throughout the activities of WP2, lack of time has frequently been cited as the principal constraint on collaboration. This is, perhaps, not entirely surprising, given the political pressures and demands made on policy stakeholders, and the commercial pressures on games companies. This risk can be conceptualised as an opportunity cost, with the benefits accruing from each incremental increase in collaboration being compared with the potential benefits from other urgent and contractually required activities. However, there is an additional factor. In seeking authenticity of interactions with stakeholders by addressing real world issues beyond the funded workplan the project created an imbalance. The time of GREAT researchers is paid for out of project funds, but policy stakeholders, although they have funding streams, need to make time available within schedules which are already full. Non-professional participants (e.g. interested citizens, and volunteers in civic organisations) are not paid at all. As Marina Kyriakou of Urban Gorillas succinctly expressed it in an interview "it's difficult to have commitment from people who are not paid to do this or cannot allocate time." This imbalance has been a constant factor throughout the work of WP2 during the full case studies and has constrained participation by and collaboration with stakeholders. This has been most obvious in the termination of collaborations with New Automotive, and DG ENER, described in the summaries above, but it has also conditioned the types of collaborations conducted in most case studies. This risk goes beyond opportunity cost to potentially include a sense of injustice and alienation.

Effectiveness and efficiency

RQ 1.2 asks "How effective are games-based activities in eliciting, representing and communicating citizens' views on policy dilemmas?", while RQ 1.3 asks "How efficient is the use of games-based activities in eliciting, representing and communicating citizens' views on policy dilemmas?". WP2 only addresses the design stages of the GREAT method, but it has generated evidence which helps to answer these questions.

Given the lower than expected level of collaboration from stakeholders, both in terms of numbers and of intensity, design activities have depended more than expected on small group conversations and on one-to-one conversations between GREAT staff and individual stakeholders, especially when working directly with decision makers. It is

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therefore unsurprising that the strong personal contacts were a success factor. This could depend on a strong alignment between individuals at a chance meeting (e.g. in GCS3 Green Jobs), or, more frequently, on leveraging existing networks among the project team. These networks were typically personal rather than institutional. This dependency on individuals was also a risk factor, because they could become unavailable for personal reasons, as was the case in GCS2 Waterwise, and GCS6 New Automotive

In the same way that collaboration from policy stakeholders has been less intensive than had been hoped, engagement with more diverse stakeholders and to generate wider participation have not been very successful. For example it was not possible to maintain the participation of civic groups in the Die Grünen, preparatory case study Frankfurt, reported in D2.1, and the response to the public data sprint, reported in D5.3, was very disappointing. In practice, diversity of engagement in the project has been achieved not in the design stage, but rather in the games-based activities delivered to participants, which are out of scope for this deliverable.

We observe that policy stakeholders at all levels (governments, agencies, NGOs) are continually dealing with risk by balancing political and financial pressures which are critical to their survival, and that bringing additional actors into policy or strategy development process is a complicating factor. From this perspective it is not surprising that in none of the case studies conducted has GREAT found a desire among policy stakeholders for truly collaborative design of policy or strategy, or for the diversification of the design of interventions. On the contrary, having given their branding to a case study, policy makers and policy implementers were understandably very concerned to control the risk presented by the scope of the studies so that their institutional positions were not contradicted implicitly or explicitly in GREAT activities. This can be seen in the requirement of DFFE for a formal memorandum of understanding to specify the extent of the collaboration. It was also expressed in the interviews conducted by WP2, which included a specific question on this topic.

- Sílvia Jardon Tovar of UNDP said that while bringing in other actors could probably have provided enhancements " I'm not sure if in this particular initiative it should have been the way forward".
- Marios Antoniou of Cyprus Ministry of Education felt that appropriate time for other groups to contribute would be "in the next phase, the pilot phase".
- Marina Kyriakou of Urban Gorillas, as mentioned above, argued that "it's difficult to have commitment from people who are not paid to do this".

In many cases, in order to maintain the viability of the design process, the model of collaboration moved inexorably from true co-design to more of a consultancy model in which rich input and feedback was sought from policy stakeholders on a focused inquiry. To this extent, and without undermining the successful outcomes of the GREAT case studies as a whole, WP2 has provided evidence that a truly collaborative design of interventions, and the inclusion of wider groups is neither effective nor efficient given the political and organisational realities under which policy makers, policy implementers and policy enablers operate. WP2 prepared an initial set of templates for the design of activities with wider groups of stakeholders, and a method for documenting them. These have been useful as inspiration for case study leads in designing activities. They have been used directly, primarily in the Waterwise case study, and in Green Roofs, but to a much lesser extent than expected. This aligns with the pressure to move to a consultancy model in response to pressure on the availability of stakeholders.

In section 5.6, above, we describe the challenges involved in collaborating with games studios, particularly in the current economic and political climate. As discussed in section 7.5, below, this suggests that while these collaborations are highly effective in terms of data generated, the effort involved in setting up the collaboration is substantial, which reduces their efficiency.

Benefits and risks as perceived by researchers and stakeholders

At the close of the project, the evidence that has been gathered indicates that the experience of collaborative design in GREAT reflects the differing expectations of policy stakeholders (who were broadly satisfied with the collaborations which had taken place), and researchers (who were continually striving for greater richness in the design process and were frustrated when this did not materialise). These expectations correspond to differing benefits and risks which could emerge from such collaborations. For stakeholders, the key benefits are access to valuable information about their operating environment, and the risks are the opportunity costs incurred in time invested in the design process, and disruption to their management of the political environment and alliances with their own stakeholders. For researchers, the key benefit is the opportunity to explore initiatives which extend current practice in the policy sphere and create new conversations about policy, and the risk is that those innovations will be too cautious. Clearly, the risk to researchers conflicts with the risk to policy stakeholders. Given that policy stakeholders are invited collaborators with no contractual obligations or financial compensation it is inevitable that the policy

stakeholders' interests will prevail, as they always have the option to withdraw. In this context, the successful design work reported here represents a negotiated balance of interest between the collaborating parties, which could not have been substantially changed without threatening the viability of the collaboration.

7.2 Timing of collaborations

Commitment to a case study, and to collaboration in the design of GREAT interventions, requires stakeholders to invest time in understanding and coordinating with the project. This reflected a genuine interest in and use for the data which would be generated. However, the timing of the collaborations was crucial, with both positive and negative consequences. To maintain momentum, it is essential that policy stakeholders have a pressing dilemma which they want to address in the case study. However, the need itself is not sufficient. For example, the DFFE in South Africa, in GCS7 Prosper, was unable to collaborate fully until a memorandum of understanding had been signed, a process which required formal steps in the organisation. These took more time than could be scheduled for the design stage of the intervention. Similarly, Play2Act2 was constrained by the need of UNDP to give formal approval a new question set for the PlanetPlay survey app which carried its brand. This could not be provided within the case study timeframe, constraining the options for design decisions. On the other hand, it was possible to organise Beat the Heat within a short time frame because the Ministry of Education in Cyprus had clear and immediate dilemma in how to implement a policy on environmental education. In the policy sphere, conditions change rapidly, and this can also impact on collaboration. For example, collaboration with New Automotive was impacted by a UK government decision which suddenly made all their targets much easier to hit, and by the decision to expand New Automotive activities to Germany, with organisational requirements that distracted from the case study.

7.3 Contributions to partner strategies and infrastructure

An important contribution of work of WP2 has been to contribute to the **development of new strategies and infrastructure in the services offered by project partners**. SGI developed DiBL 2.0 SGI developed DiBL 2.0 (see D3.1 for Technical Specification and D3.3 for MVP description), largely in response to the requirements of the use case of the GCS7 Prosper and GCS2 Waterwise, but also earlier case studies such as GCS3 Green Jobs and GCS4 Rooftop Revolution. The design and play-through of the complex structure of the Prosper game, provided validation for the DiBL2.

PlanetPlay have developed a new CMS system to manage the design and deployment of their survey app activities within host games (see section 5.7 above). Interventions designed with UNDP have also shown that the use of in-game placement of embedded activities agreed with studios on a one-to-one basis is far more effective than the purchase of paid-for 'playable advertisements', with consequent impact on the strategy adopted by PlanetPlay in designing interventions. This strategy implied an even greater focus on management of the relationship with studios and again meant that personal contacts were even more important than anticipated.

7.4 Insight into the GREAT methodology

The work of WP2 reported here, and throughout the project, provides a valuable perspective on the first three steps of the case study cycle. In broad terms the division of the design process into three steps has been validated through the successful mapping of plans and activities onto the templates provided in the appendix. The three incremental outputs have also been generated in the case studies (i.e. design challenge, design brief and wireframes). However, some important distinctions have emerged. The process worked was a more natural fit for DiBL than for PlanetPlay, because DiBL involves a broadly conventional development of a game (in this case a serious game), starting from a blank slate and considering interactions, interface etc. These can be represented in shared artefacts, including Miro boards, to support collaboration. For PlanetPlay, the basic structure of the PlanetPlay survey app is established, and design is largely limited to visual design, and development of new question types, custom-questions from studios and player journey. As a result, the concept of 'wireframe' was less appropriate. Rather, the work involved strategies for embedding, establishing collaborations with games studios who can host the app, and supporting studios in embedding the app.

The steps 1-3 assume a handover of the output of step 3 to a development team who would create a game-based activity to be delivered to players. In practice the development process was much more agile than this, particularly in step 3. The DiBL developers were able to collaborate with iteratively with designers both in Miro and in the DiBL platform itself, so that step 3 overlapped with step 4. In the case of PlanetPlay, the development did take delivery of the requirements, but the configuration of the survey app was swift, and included issues of where to deploy and how, which are in essence step 3 questions.

In the methodology, each of the three steps has four items which will be produced. All of these were fulfilled, with the exception of "Indicators of attitudes and preferences"

in step 1. It proved difficult for participants to understand what this meant in practice. It was also hard to conceive of indicators in the abstract, before having defined a game scenario and activities in step 2. In step 2 the “Data to be gathered and pipeline” became redundant, as the response was always to gather all the interactions with players, and to store them on the platform.

Replicability

As regards dilemma games, the methodology worked well and has led to the successful use of games with respondents and the generation of valuable data. No barriers to replicability of the design process have been identified, although the constraints described in this section should be born in mind.

As regards game studios, GREAT has successfully gathered data through collaborations with 70 game studios, and in this sense, it has been demonstrated that this approach to consulting games players on their views is replicable. However, as observed in GCS2(b) Waterwise, step 3, obtaining the agreement of game studios is a delicate task, depending on excellent relations with the studio, and an understanding of the studio’s motivations and concerns. Even if these conditions are in place, internal changes in the studio can lead to disengagement at a late stage in particular instances, as was the case in both GCS2(b) Waterwise and GCS9 Play2Act3. The GREAT partners have no special leverage over game studios to make this data gathering method viable, but partner PlanetPlay has very extensive relevant knowledge and skills which anyone replicating the approach would need to develop. The evidence of collaboration in GREAT indicates that these collaborations will remain alliances of convenience corresponding to aligned interests, facilitated by networks of personal and professional contacts. Moreover, success in establishing collaboration with stakeholders may be contingent on unplanned meetings, and the fortunate meshing of timeframes. The work conducted in GREAT is therefore a testament to what is possible in a collaboration between policy stakeholders, game studios and academics, but it is not easy to achieve, and the process cannot be reduced to a step-by-step guide.

Publications

WP2 is covers a subsection of the case study cycle, and its results should be seen in the context of the deliverables and publications which have emerged from WP4, which is responsible for case studies as a whole. A number of papers have been published which discuss the design of interventions within the context of GREAT case studies, for example.

- Hollins et al. (2024) summarise collaboration with UNDP on the design of GCS1, Exploratory Case Study.
- Griffiths et al. (2025), discusses the constraints and opportunities for stakeholders in the design of interventions, in the context work with games studios and UNDP in GCS1.
- Koller and Kieslinger (2024) summarise the collaborative design of the GCS3, Green Jobs in Austria.
- Merry, Zachariou and Yau (2025) describe the collaborative design process leading to the GREAT Green Roofs study in Cyprus
- Watson et al. (2024) describe how short data sprints using data generated in GREAT activities can be used to stimulate discussion on climate issues with citizens or stakeholders.
- Yau et al. (2024) discuss the co-design of pilot games with citizens and policy stakeholders to increase pilot action in relation to six GREAT case studies.

However, the evidence gathered in the course of the GREAT project and documented in D2.1, D2.2 and D2.3, has by no means been exhausted, providing the opportunity for further insight into the dynamics, benefits, risks, enablers and constraints relating to collaborative design of games-based interventions. In particular, it is planned that the interviews described in this deliverable the development of a paper which will examine the benefits and constraints perceived by stakeholders in relation to collaborations of the type which have been conducted in GREAT.

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Annexes

The annexes to this deliverable are in separate files, because they are confidential, and they are also large documents

Annex 1 consists of all the planning and reporting templates for the activities carried out, as was done for D2.1 and D2.2.

Annex 2 is a zip file with supplementary material referred to in the main text.

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